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Teacher's Motivation for and experience with Using Flipped Classroom in a PBL-Environment

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INTRODUCTION

In higher educations awareness of, and experimenting with, technology-enhanced learning through the use of Flipped Classroom (FC) has increased during the last couple of years [1]. This is happening while educators involved in FC do not fully know the pedagogical concept of how to effectively translate the flipped classroom into practice [2][3]. At Aalborg University (AAU) a new research project: “Future directions for PBL in a digital age” is dealing with; how digital technologies can enhance problem- and project-based learning (PBL) at AAU [4]. Part of this project is researching the use of FC in a PBL environment as an example of using digitised aspects in existing curriculum. This paper has focus on why and how some teachers at AAU are working with FC. The following questions have led the research: What motivate some teachers at AAU to use the flipped classroom approach? Which opportunities and concerns have the teachers at AAU experienced when using FC in a PBL environment?

1 BACKGROUND

Since 1974 AAU has developed principles and models for Problem and Project Based Learning (The Aalborg PBL model), based on constructivist and social learning approaches emphasizing that learning is an active process, which take place through social relations. The PBL model highlights student-centered learning [5]. The AAU principles for problem-based and project-organized work [6] implies a structure for all educational programs where half of the semester is used on courses and the other half on student-organized project work (semester projects). Each semester is based on a curriculum and has a theme guiding the goals and content of the learning. In students semester projects there is a high emphasis of using the PBL competences related to working problem based and project- organized in groups (generic or transferable skills) [6]. Courses are meant to give students the necessary background knowledge for making their projects, and each course has their own exam. All teachers at AAU are working in a PBL environment based on active, social and student-centered teaching/learning approach is used, but there are different way of practising PBL. At courses a fully packed curriculum and course exams might cause that students have to prioritize where they will use their resources [3] which can cause less attention on e.g. students project-work and the important PBL competences. Some teachers have been challenged to change the traditional way of teaching their courses, and have seen FC as a new possibility for improving their courses. FC is in literature described as a pedagogical strategy used in courses [1] [2] and the research on FC in a PBL environment is in this paper therefore framed by PBL in a course-work setting.

1.1 FLIPPED CLASSROOM

From reviewing the literature on FC in higher education, it becomes apparent that there is a lacking consensus on what constitutes a flipped classroom approach. Lage et al. defined flipped (or inverted) classrooms as: “Inverting the classroom means that events that have traditionally taken place inside the classroom now are taking

place outside the classroom and vice versa” [7]. This definition presents a re-ordering of in-class and out-of-class activities and thereby presents a radical change from what is traditionally seen as teaching practice. However it is also claimed that ICT has to be an important part of FC because of the computer-based individual instruction outside the classroom, but also as a possibility for the interactive group learning activities inside the classroom [3]. FC is a rather new pedagogical concept for teachers to try out and newer studies tell more about both the teaching methodology and pedagogical approaches connected to FC.

The didactic method for FC is found in the technology-enhanced involvement that both students and teachers experience. Bliuc et al. describe it as a “systematic combination of co-present (face-to-face) interaction and technologically-mediated interactions between students, teachers and learning resources” [8]. The technology-based resources are often seen as videos [2][9]: small clips from YouTube or videos of teachers’ own presentations [10]. The video resources are often supplemented by quizzes or multiple-choice tests. This serves as a reassurance that the students are actually watching the videos and can be a monitoring of how well the material is used and understood [11].

Using videos for preparation purposes opens up new opportunities; like reaching students who prefer a more visual learning style or would like a greater flexibility to go through lecture presentations [12]. The pedagogical ideas and framework of the FC approach is built on encouraging students to get involved in interactive and high-order activities by giving more opportunities to engage in active learning [9]. By moving lecture time to out of class activities, the in-class learning activities can become more interactive and student-centered [11]. The pedagogical approach of both PBL and FC thereby seems to aim for similar learning approaches. A pilot study of the interaction between the two approaches is therefore carried out to find if FC could be part of the AAU pedagogical approach.

2 METHODS

The investigation presented in this paper was conducted, interviewing 10 PBL experienced AAU-teachers who are currently using, or has previously used FC in their course teaching. Their way of doing FC is diverse, but they have all introduced video material as preoperational material to their course teaching. The research presented is a part of the initial empirical data, which was acquired through the on-going exploratory case studies [13][14] at five study programmes within Engineering, Science and Humanities all using the FC approach. Semi-structured interviews [15], lasting approximately 30-45 minutes each with the 10 teachers using FC have given insight to the teachers’ personal experience of working with FC. The Interviews have been focused primarily on understanding 1) the teachers’ motivation for using FC, and 2) their individual experiences with using FC. The interviews have been coded in relation to the content and four of the central code themes will guide the analysis of this research: *i) Motivation for using FC, ii) Using the FC technology, iii) In-class activities when using FC, and iv) Knowledge production in FC.* The

phenomenological research method [16], has giving insight to the teachers' personal understandings. These data have been supplemented with observations of a few of the FC course lectures. These observations have given the research an outside look at the FC teaching practice. As it is a phenomenological research it is primarily the interviews that have been used for the data analyse but the observations have guided and reinsured that the change reported by the teachers are not presented as overly positive as self reporting is criticized for [17]. The teachers possessed a varying degree of experience with using FC and in the presentation of the empirical data it will be stated if the teacher is experienced (defined as: have used FC on several course sessions over more than a year) or as more novice teachers. This differentiating of the teachers has been made because earlier research has shown that a lot of start up problems when implementing FC can occur and therefore influence the experience of working with FC [12]. The teachers' names are anonymized, and presented as letters from A to J.

3 THE FLIPPED CLASSROOM

In the following sections, we present and discuss the teachers' motivation and experiences having organized and used the FC approach. We have structured the findings within the four above-mentioned analytically coded themes.

3.1 Teachers' motivation for using FC

The interviewed teachers have all by own initiative chosen to experiment with FC and this shows a great engagement and personal motivation because it takes a lot of resources for teachers to engage in FC. We found this motivation grounded primarily in three reasons: 1) *Problems getting students to reach the required academic level, following the learning goals of the course*. A motivation can thereby be related to insufficient previous teaching and outcome of former teaching practice. One of the experienced FC teacher's states that trying out FC was some kind of "damage control" (A) because her students missed a lot of basic skills. They were demotivated and found the class very difficult, therefore many students did not pass exam. Another motivational reason for using FC is framed as 2) *FC seems to be timesaving and more efficient*. A more novice teacher states "FC would give more time for discussions in class" (D). A general understanding between the teachers is that FC creates more time together with the students. All teachers agree, independently of their experience, that they need time for "hands on" interaction, supervision/facilitation and guidance in relation to the more abstract understanding of the academic content of the course. They want to cut down time spent on the traditional teacher-led activities in the classroom and create more time for the interactive and student-centred activities. This leads to the third motivational reason for using the FC approach: 3) *The pedagogical ideas of interactive and student-led teaching*. Pedagogical ideas based on interactive as well as social and student-centred learning has also been a motivating factor for changing the teaching practice. The motivation for changing to FC might implies that previous approaches in the course teaching may not have been satisfying and they see a need for change

which can create more time to interact with the students and establish a more active and student-centered learning approach.

3.2 The FC technology – Time saving or time consuming?

The AAU teachers' motivation in saving time becomes challenged as soon as the teachers start producing their own FC video presentations with sound and/or voice over, finding instructive clips from other media, quizzes, exercises etc. Furthermore the Moodle platform has caused problems for most of the teachers (A,B,C,D,G,I). The resources given to the teachers using FC have been inadequate, as the teachers have used many extra hours on the technology. One of the novice teachers have had a lot of problems recording the lectures. He had problems with the physical settings when recording and had technical problems with the sound (I). The self-produced FC material requires both technological skills and a lot of time. The motivation of FC to be time saving and efficient also has to be seen in the light of the time consuming process of producing the FC material.

3.3 Pedagogical opportunities - in-class activities

Most of the teachers using the approach are, despite difficulties working with the technology, very engaged in continuing using the FC approach. One of the novice FC teacher states that FC gives him half an hour more per lecture where he can do exercises together with the students (I). Other teachers state that they use less time going through text material that are given for out-of-class activities (A,B,C,G,I) and e.g. instead tells the students to ask questions if they don't understand the academic content (I). Observations of the FC courses and the teachers' experiences though tells us that implementing the interactive exercises is rather difficult. An experienced FC teacher states that "It is still the in-class exercises that we need to get working better" (A). The FC approach might thereby create more time for interactive learning in the classroom and the involved teachers have in some cases been able to find alternatives to the traditional lecture teaching, but it requires a lot of resources and when using a lot of time on producing the FC material, it can be difficult to find time and resources focusing on the exercises. The teachers though reports that it have had an effect on reflecting their own teaching strategies and methods (A,B,C,D,I,J). "The process connected to FC have started us to reflect our own pedagogical methods and being much more aware of new opportunities"(A,B)

3.4 Knowledge production in FC – Reaching a higher academic level

In the interviews we found an interesting understanding of how to reach a higher academic level when using the FC approach. It seems to some of the teachers that not all academic knowledge necessarily benefits from being flipped. One of the teacher's state: "The content has to be easy to understand when it is to be presented by video" (I). Another teacher also express this concern saying: "They [the students] need to read the text to reach a higher understanding. The text material, because it might be complex and abstract, can make students wonder and reflect... the video is another medium and it doesn't make you reflect in the same way" (H). These quotes indicate that the learning activities when using flipped classroom might change the

pedagogical learning approach. An experienced teacher evolves on why and how this change in practice is done: “The biggest problems we found, is that the students often find them [the videos] too long and they are not interactive – so they can just fall asleep watching them like TV. So we chopped them up so they are 6-8 minutes long and focusing on a specific topic”(C). The content of what the students are given is thereby changed, and this can affect the knowledge production. Quizzes are used by one of the teachers to make the videos interactive (C) through integrating the quizzes in the videos. This approach have had positive feedback from the students and they ask for more – especially focused on exams (C). Quizzes might have a great effect on creating more interactive learning, but the interaction level and reaching a higher learning level can still be discussed. An experienced teacher explains her use of quizzes (by her called exercises): “Those are just extremely simple things, almost just like: do you remember what you just heard? It's just to check whether the students follow the videos before the class.”(A). At an instructive level, quizzes may be used to facilitate factual knowledge, but quizzes may also be used to support reflection and higher-level learning, depending on the kind of questions (only one right answer or many possibly right answers?) and depending on the kind of detailed feedback given for the students to reflect upon [18].

4 SUMMARY OF RESULTS AND CONCLUDING REMARKS

Investigating the use of FC in PBL environments have in our study given insight into why teachers at AAU are experimenting with using FC in their course teaching. Pedagogical problems using the traditional lecturing structure and unsatisfying teaching results from previous courses have motivated teachers to change their practice. New and more interactive learning strategies are wished to improve the course teaching. The motivation to change teaching through FC in a course-work setting can thereby be seen as supportive in a PBL environment. The teachers experiences also show that the FC approach can create alternatives to the more traditional teacher- centered lectures. Some concerns are however important to encounter e.g. using FC approach in the PBL environment. Technology and product of FC material have shown to be difficult and very time consuming, and the resources used on this part of the FC approach can risk to become too overwhelming and time consuming, and can become a barrier for developing interactive and student-centered learning material. Furthermore we have seen some concerns about the ICT impact on the teaching content and the didactic approach to knowledge production. A risc of simplifying the curriculum content when producing good video presentations can have an unknown affect on students learning. This concern should be encountered when applying FC in a PBL environment where student- centered and problem based learning is essential.

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